

The Importance of the Community Mediation. An Example of Practical Course

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Abstract: This paper aims to present the importance of community mediation current social life. As a result, authors can organize a mediation course community in which to express their design and their applications about the subject

Keywords: community mediator, mediation, community mediation

JEL Classification: Y20, Y80, Z13

Community mediator is the person who connects groups in the community and local authorities. Most times can be a member of these communities. To streamline the organizational effort for better organization of community life, we must coordinate efforts following a common strategy, which should be decided together with those concerned. Discrimination and marginalization are phenomena that can be reduced in a community and even eliminated through civics open, comprehensive and respect for diversity.

Being a good community mediator means to use your power of expression and persuasion to change things for the better. There are specialized organizations and public figures who engaged in community mediation. These organizations or leaders speak on the basis of surveys and reports, often subjective or material reasons.

Your opinion should become important for officials and elect. Public opinion must be respected in a democracy, especially in terms of drafting legislation, public policies and how public money should be spent.

To have an informed opinion you should be aware of legislation concerning discrimination and to the public policies and budget. To solve problems, to correct mistakes and to prevent new errors have to get involved, to participate in public debate. Being an activist against discrimination is not a trade or an honorific title reserved for a few chosen men, but a state of mind.

Parents are concerned about the fate of their children. Community mediators are concerned with the fate of the communities they represent! Whether you have 5 minutes per week or 5 hours a day, using the following tips can effectively become a community mediator:

1. Familiarize yourself with the laws concerning people's lives in the community. The right to not have to follow it, there is a lot of information on all kinds of support legislation: written, audio, internet.
2. Subscribe to newsletter dealing with the organizations or issue that interests you. They will keep abreast of legislative proposals and law enforcement issues in the field that interests you.
3. Keep in touch with elected officials (mayor, local councilors, and parliamentarians). Politicians are people with different experiences from those of the common man and it is likely that they never had to do with experience of discrimination. Therefore it is normal that they do not understand the issues and implications discrimination laws regarding this issue. No need to know all legislation concerning discrimination or be affiliated with an organization's important to talk to your representatives. If he was going to pass a law or a local council decision, they would like to hear your opinion, informed before voting than to receive letters and phone calls of outrage after the decision.

4. Write them develop public policy experts. Like if your phone your elected officials want to hear from you because they want to be reelected. Explain how it affects or will affect a certain law discriminated against a particular group or marginalized. These explanations and examples will be useful to elected officials. In response you can expect a thank you letter or a bill proposed by that representative.
5. Speak only what you know well. Tell your family, friends, even people you meet by chance on issues of discrimination and about viable solutions to these problems. If you happen to encounter a person running for an elected post, not flee from it. Ask her about what he intends to do to fight against discrimination, and then tell him your opinion.
6. Make public your opinion. Call the radio; write letters and e-mails to editors of newspapers. Explain your position, illustrated the importance of combating discrimination against them and present solutions to problems encountered. Place posters and organize meetings in your community to discuss policies to combat various forms of discrimination. As activists against discrimination does not have to fight alone. Instead, you must attract and involved as many as possible in your actions. It is very important to create a diverse team that you fill in activity; otherwise you will be in danger of becoming ineffective.
7. Vote! It seems an elementary, but it is very important that you use your right. You can even do more, helping in the campaign a candidate who supports the fight against discrimination and interests of the group to which you belong. The experience and expertise can help your candidate / nominee to clarify his stance on the issue of discrimination, a problem that affects many people / voters.

The first step to become a community mediator to promote good community problems you represent and diversity of ideas and facts is to get familiar with this issue and to learn to talk about it. Your personal experiences are probably quite motivating for you, but it is hard for others to understand the problem from your point of view. So it is advisable to document about data and statistics objectives and familiarize yourself with the general aspects of the problem and, especially, the correct terms to describe a situation (ex. «Children's rights») or a particular group (e.g. «problem children»). There are still many stereotypes and prejudices on discriminated and marginalized. For this reason it is important to know all the aspects and present them as efficiently as possible, to have a higher impact in the

fight against prejudices and stereotypes society. Dry statistics and concrete cases have the same effect as an argument or a metaphor emotional well-built plastic. Discrimination and marginalization are real phenomena, every day, affecting a very large number of people.

1. Mediator activity in public policy

All policies can be applied locally. All laws and public policy implications and local effects and are justified by specific local needs. It is an obvious truth that politicians in central government forget too easily. Laws exist for citizens and must be the result of the combined efforts of public officials, and therefore the mediator Community to promote them or to supervise their proper application. Community mediator and promote legislative initiatives. You just need to understand how the government works and how to be effective in working with officials. There are lots of different ways to reach decision makers in order to communicate our thoughts on mediation Community.

Community mediation course could have the following objectives: training of specialists from local institutions and NGOs on issues of communication and mediation in order to solve common problems of their work easy. The target group would be made up of specialists with higher and middle of municipalities, prefectures, municipal councils or NGOs. The main themes of a possible mediation course community could relate to: the concepts of communication, negotiation, mediation; Community mediation necessity and goals; mediation - essential activity in civil society; functions and dysfunctions of mediation; the mediator's role in the local community; Mediation practical schemes; future activities of community mediation.

2. Here schedule such a course:

Course title Community Mediation

Code, Location, period

Course Program

Sunday,	
15.30-16.00	Course opening. Presenting the participants and the agenda
16.00-17.30	Course goals

Monday,	
09.00 - 10.30	Introduction to the course issues. The concepts of communication, negotiation and mediation
10.30 - 11.00	Coffee break
11.00 - 12.30	Principles, theories and applications regarding mediation
12.30 - 14.00	Lunch
14.00 - 15.30	Practical relevance of mediation
15.30 - 16.00	Coffee break
16.00 - 17.30	Specifics of mediation as a form of communication

Tuesday,	
09.00 - 10.30	The need and purposes of community mediation
10.30 - 11.00	Coffee break
11.00 - 12.30	The mediator profession
12.30 - 14.00	Lunch
14.00 - 15.30	Conceptual and practical mediation schemes
15.30 - 16.00	Coffee break
16.00 - 17.30	The typical mediator

Wednesday,	
09.00 - 10.30	Mediator's role in the local community
10.30 - 11.00	Coffee break
11.00 - 12.30	Mediator's relation with the institutional environment
12.30 - 14.00	Lunch
14.00 - 15.30	Mediation - an essential activity in the civil society
15.30 - 16.00	Coffee break
16.00 - 17.30	Mediation in local collectivities

Thursday,	
09.00 - 10.30	Fundraising activities in local communities
10.30 - 11.00	Coffee break
11.00 - 12.30	Mediator's role in fundraising activities
12.30 - 14.00	Lunch
14.00 - 15.30	Conflicts in the local communities
15.30 - 16.00	Coffee break
16.00 - 17.30	Mediator's role in solving the conflicts

Friday,	
09.00 - 10.30	The European mediator. Functions and roles/
10.30 - 11.00	Coffee break
11.00 - 12.30	Functions and dysfunctions of mediation at local level
12.30 - 14.00	Lunch
14.00 - 15.30	Internship for the European mediator qualification
15.30 - 16.00	Coffee break
16.00 - 17.30	The future of community mediation activities

Saturday,	
09.00-10.30	Test for the evaluation of the knowledge acquired in the course
10.30-11.00	Coffee break
11.00-12.30	Discussing the test results
12.30-13.00	Presenting the course evaluation sheet
13.00-14.30	Conclusions, handing out the certificates and closing the course

LECTURERS:

Name and surname	The institution where they work

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